

A glimpse into the viticulture of Roman Lusitania: morphometric analysis of charred grape pips from Torre dos Namorados, Portugal

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Abstract

The Roman site of Torre dos Namorados (Fundão, Beiras region, central Portugal) is a rare find, identified as a Roman vicus (village), with evidence of making wine and olive oil. During the archaeological campaigns of 2006-2007 a rectangular Roman lacus musti (must, grape juice, settling vat) was found, built with tegulae (tiles) and bricks, and containing thousands of charred grape pips and skins. By using a stepwise linear discriminant analysis method (LDA), a morphological comparison was made of these archaeological grape pips and with a reference collection of modern pips, both from cultivated Portuguese varieties of *Vitis vinifera* L. ssp. *vinifera* and from wild vines of *Vitis vinifera* L. ssp. *sylvestris*, to study similarities between them. The modern grape pips were charred in order to obtain suitable material to compare with the archaeological pips. The statistical analysis showed a clear association between the archaeological grape pips and wild grapes, suggesting that these were used for making wine in Roman times. The data presented here represent the first systematic study of Roman viticulture in the Lusitanian province of Iberia.

Keywords Charred grape pips · Morphometric analysis · Roman viticulture · Lusitanian province · *Vitis* · Portuguese germplasm bank

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Introduction

The grape family (Vitaceae Juss.) belongs to the order Vitales Juss. ex Bercht. & J.Presl, and it consists of 17 genera and about 950 species, most of them tendril-bearing vines, among which is *Vitis vinifera* L. (grapevine) (Wen et al. 2018). Grapevine is the most planted crop in the world, covering approximately 7.3 million ha (FAOSTAT 2022). The economic, social and cultural value of the grapevine has been known since ancient times, for the harvesting and consumption of its fruit, and their use for making wine. Cultivars of *Vitis vinifera* ssp. *vinifera* (cultivated grape) derive from domestication of *Vitis vinifera* ssp. *sylvestris* (Gmelin) Hegi (wild grape) (Scossiroli 1988; Zohary 1995; Sefc et al. 2003; Imazio et al. 2006; This et al. 2006; Cunha et al. 2007a; Zohary et al. 2012). The wild grape is a heliophilous liana that grows in riverside and lowland deciduous and semi-deciduous woodlands, in a distribution range that extends from the Atlantic coast of Europe to the western Himalayas (Levadoux 1956; Arnold et al. 1998; Zohary 1995; Zohary et al. 2012).

According to archaeological and archaeobotanical evidence, domestication of the grape took place in the Caucasus and the Middle East between 6000 and 3000 BCE (Negrul 1946; Arnold et al. 1998; Zohary 1995; Olmo 1996; Zohary et al. 2012). The most ancient archaeobotanical evidence of domesticated grapes comes from the Jordan valley and dates back to the Chalcolithic (McGovern 2003; Barnard et al. 2011; Zohary et al. 2012). Recent genomic analyses suggest that there was a single domestication event that occurred in western Asia and this was followed by numerous introgressive hybridizations which then spread to wild vines in Europe (Freitas et al. 2021; Magris et al. 2021).

In the eastern Mediterranean, archaeobotanical evidence of early viticulture has been discovered in Greece from Neolithic sites (Dikili Tash) from the 5th millennium BCE, and Egypt from Old Kingdom tombs (ca. 2700 BCE) (Kroll 1991; McGovern et al. 1997; Valamoti et al. 2007; Pagnoux et al. 2015). Archaeobotanical remains of grape pips have also been recovered in the western Mediterranean area from various archaeological sites (Zohary et al. 2012) and also from Sardinia and Sicily (Ucchesu et al. 2015; Moricca et al. 2021). In Sardinia, the study of grape pips from a Middle Bronze Age Nuragic settlement provided the first evidence of primitive cultivated *V. vinifera* in this area (Ucchesu et al. 2015). In the Italian peninsula, the increasing presence of *Vitis* from the Iron Age and onwards could be an indicator of the beginning of viticulture there (Marvelli et al. 2013). In Spain, archaeobotanical evidence of winemaking has been found in Phoenician archaeological sites from the 7th century BCE (Evans 2018). In southern France, archaeobotanical remains link the beginning of viticulture with the foundation of the Greek city of Massalia (modern Marseille) in 600 BCE (Brun 2011; Bouby et al. 2013). In Portugal, the study of pollen from the site of Paul dos Patudos dos Alpiarça showed an increase of 33% in *Vitis* pollen during the 7th century BCE compared with

more ancient layers (Fletcher et al. 2007). A small number of grape pips have been recovered from various Iron Age sites in northwest Portugal (Tereso et al. 2011; Tereso 2012; Tereso et al. 2013b; Tereso and Cruz 2014; Seabra 2015), but there is little evidence so far of *V. vinifera* in the rest of Portuguese territory during this period, including Phoenician sites (Rego and Aira Rodríguez 1993; Barros 1998, 2001; Queiroz et al. 2006; Queiroz and Mateus 2007; Arruda 2008). Grape pips become more frequent and quantitatively more important, both in rural and urban Roman sites (Almeida and Veiga Ferreira 1967; Pinto da Silva 1988; Queiroga 1992; Almeida 1996; Tereso et al. 2011, 2013a; Tereso and Cruz 2014; Savo et al. 2016; Peña-Chocarro et al. 2019; Currás et al. 2021). In addition, the archaeological discovery of several lagares (wine press structures), dating from the 1st century CE, in the Roman province of Lusitania, which broadly corresponds to southern and central Portugal together with part of western central Spain, and the production in Lisbon between the 2nd and 3rd centuries CE of Lusitania type 3 amphorae for exporting wine (Fabião 1998), seem to indicate local growing of grapes, which was intensive and widespread (Pereira and Silvino 2018) (Almeida 1996; Pereira 2017).

The discovery in 2006 of thousands of charred grape pips from the Roman winery of Torre dos Namorados in Fundão is unusual considering the rarity of these remains in Portugal. The high concentration of pips found in this archaeological context represents an excellent opportunity to study the nature of these remains. The morphometric analysis of the Torre dos Namorados grape pips is the first study of this kind on Portuguese material.

The aim of this study of these archaeological grape pips is to contribute to the understanding of Roman viticulture in Portugal.

The site of Torre dos Namorados and its surroundings

Torre dos Namorados (Fundão, Castelo Branco) is an archaeological site classified as a Roman *vicus*, and located in the southern part of Beiras region, central Portugal (Fig. 1). A *vicus* was a population nucleus, composed of houses and buildings forming a village in a rural area, that was not only connected with primary production activities such as farming (Pérez Losada 2002), but could also have helped the capital of the *civitas* (city, Roman political and administrative area) manage its vast *territorium* (area belonging to a regional market city), form a settlement and use the natural resources of the region.

Fig. 1 The location of the Torre dos Namorados archaeological site in the Iberian Peninsula

After the conquest of the Iberian Peninsula by Rome in 16/13 BCE, the subsequent territorial reorganization divided it into three provinces, *Hispania Citerior*, *Hispania Ulterior Lusitania* and *Hispania Ulterior Baetica*, with much of today's Portugal within the province of *Lusitania*, with its capital in *Emerita Augusta* (now Mérida, Spain).

According to the data currently available, the *vicus* of Torre dos Namorados was included in the *territorium* of the *civitas Igaeditanorum* (Idanha-a-Velha/Idanha-a-Nova) belonging to the *conventus* (political-administrative region that included several cities) *Emeritensis*. The capital of the *civitas Igaeditanorum*, located in Idanha-a-Velha, is mentioned in an inscription dated to 16 BCE, proving its existence when the province was re-organized (Carvalho 2007).

This territory was particularly attractive for its mineral resources, such as the Roman goldmining complex of Mina da Presa and Covão do Urso, at the base of the Serra da Malcata, Penamacor/Castelo Branco (Carvalho 2007). The region is also particularly rich in good agricultural soils for producing wine and olive oil, both extremely important in the Roman economy.

The scarcity of systematic archaeological excavations in this area does not allow us to understand the history of the known sites in detail. Nevertheless, archaeological surveys of the land surface show that the area had a markedly rural character, with small occupation sites, farms, *villae* (rare, and distinct in their construction from those of southern Lusitania) and *vici*.

The process of Romanisation seems to have brought a new type of economy, a regional road system that allowed the circulation of products and the reorganisation of the local people by expansion of pre-existing settlements together with the foundation of new ones by the Romans.

Torre dos Namorados was situated at the crossing of the main Roman road that connected the provincial capital *Augusta Emerita* (Mérida, Spain) to *Bracara Augusta* (Braga, Portugal). This road existed from the time when the *civitas* territory was reorganised and it was still there in 235-305 CE according to a milestone found at Torre dos Namorados (Fig. 2; Vaz 1977).

The surface of the site was surveyed in 2003, leading to a research project between 2004 and 2007 that included archaeological excavation. The investigation revealed an important Roman site for this region, not only because of the numerous and wide distribution of archaeological materials on the ground surface, but also because of its possible function. The latter was revealed by the presence of several structures such as parts of mills which may have been connected with wine making and extraction of olive oil, which were found in four areas of the site, Tapada da Torre, Fonte Velha, Vale Cortiço and Coitos (Fig. 3).

We do not know if these areas were all occupied at the same time because of the lack of excavations, although the archaeological finds from the surface provide some indications that Torre dos Namorados was occupied from the end of the 1st century BCE or beginning of the 1st century CE until the 5th century CE, according to the presence of fragments of Italic, South Gaulish, Hispanic, Late Hispanic and African *terra sigillata* pottery (imported fine ware) (Ângelo 2012).

Surface surveying also recovered fragments of wine amphorae produced in the Guadalquivir valley region (southern Spain) from the 1st century BCE to the 1st century CE and amphorae for holding fish products, produced in the Tejo/Sado region (central Portugal) in the 3rd to 5th centuries CE (Ângelo 2012). This pottery which was brought to Torre dos Namorados, shows the economic capability of its population.

Fig. 2 Map of the region around Torre dos Namorados showing the proposed *civitates* and the Roman road system. (Adapted from Ângelo 2012, map 1). Further information in Carvalho (2007)

Fig. 3 Torre dos Namorados vicus (rural village) areas and distribution of archaeological remains. (Adapted from Ângelo 2012, map 3)

The context of the archaeological grape pips found at Coitos

The 2006-2007 archaeological excavations in the Coitos area revealed a wine press where two rooms were identified, in which were sealed layers preserved by the collapse of the roof. Room 1 was the pressing room (*area*), square or rectangular, about 7 m wide. It was paved with quartzite pebbles which were covered in *opus signinum* (fine mortar obtained by mixing hydraulic lime and crushed ceramics) which was particularly well preserved along the walls. Room 2 contained two large cylindrical counterweights with a circular structure around the second one (Fig. 5).

The excavated material from room 2 consisted of building materials such as *tegulae* and *imbrices* (different types of tiles), bricks, *dolia* (large storage pots) and everyday pottery (coarse ware). Also noteworthy is the finding of a fragment of a Late Hispanic *terra sigillata* bowl decorated with *guilloché* patterning (Drag. 37 type) which was made ca 350-500 CE. It was found in the abandonment level of the circular structure, around the second counterweight.

A lacus musti (must settling vat) was next to to the wall of the room, consisting of a rectangular tank made of *tegulae* (tiles) and brick fragments and lined with clay mortar (Figs 4,5; Ângelo and Ribeiro 2008) and containing charred grape pips and fruit skins (Figs. 4, 5). There was evidence of burning on the wall of the room, suggesting a fire that had charred the grape remains.

The Coitos wine press would have had a screw pressing system. Both counterweights, with their upper grooves extending laterally in a V shape, had a central hole where wooden fittings and iron hooks would have been fixed to support a large wooden beam. They would also have been fitted into

the holes found in the north wall of room 1 or anchored to a vertical post (Fig. 5; Ângelo and Ribeiro 2008).

Fig. 4 a the lacus musti (must settling vat) at Torre dos Namorados; **b c** the charred grape pips found there

In the region around Torre dos Namorados, evidence of wine making has also been found at the site of Quinta da Fórnea I (Belmonte, Castelo Branco), which was probably a *villa* (Roman farm buildings and surrounding land). The finds suggest that it was occupied at the end of the 2nd century/beginning of the 3rd century CE (~ 200 CE) and was intentionally abandoned in the 4th century (Carvalho 2007). According to one author, the press of Quinta da Fórnea was in a building used for wine making, with two tanks lined with *opus signinum*, a *calcatorium* (tank where the grapes were trodden to release the juice) (5.20×3.80 m) and a settling vat (1.40×1.40 m) connected by a pipe (Pereira 2017). There have been several finds of parts of presses such as press weights from archaeological surface prospection in the territory of *civitas Igaeditarorum*, but the lack of systematic archaeological study limits information on the northern interior of the Roman province of Lusitania.

Fig. 5 a, plan of area 2 of the Torre dos Namorados site; b, c the lacus mustii (must settling vat); c, a counterweight

Materials

Archaeological grape pip samples

Charred grape pips and fruit skins were separated from sediments collected from the must settling vat, using a sieve column of different mesh sizes (0.5 mm, 2 mm, 4 mm). A total of 1,122 archaeological grape pips were obtained and analysed in this study. They were radiocarbon dated and their chronology, corresponding to the last use of the vat, coincides with the dating from the pottery. The SUERC - 81645 (GU48796) pip sample gave an uncalibrated date of $1,638 \pm 28$ BP and when calibrated, gives a 95.4% probability of being from cal AD 339-435 [76.4%]; cal AD 451-471 [2.9%]) and (cal AD 487-534 [16.1%]). Considering the probability values and the archaeological context, a date around 400 CE is considered the reference value here.

Reference samples of cultivated and wild grape pips

Modern grape pips were collected from different plants (in order to ensure the greatest morphological variability) of 35 native cultivars of *V. vinifera* ssp. *vinifera*, which came from the Coleção

Ampelográfica Nacional (CAN, (Portuguese national *Vitis* germplasm bank) of the Instituto Nacional de Investigação Agrária e Veterinária (INIAV, National Institute for Agrarian and Veterinarian Research), located at Dois Portos (Portugal) (ESM Table 1).

These cultivars were selected because they represent the most ancient grape varieties traditionally grown in this region. Moreover, they are unique Portuguese genotypes when compared with those in other Mediterranean germplasm banks (Almadanim et al. 2007; Cunha et al. 2016).

In addition, wild grape pip accessions from nine plants and four populations of *V. vinifera* ssp. *sylvestris* were collected from several riverside woods in three different river basins in Portugal for use in this study (ESM Table 2). The geographical equidistance was more than 100 km between the different populations, to avoid the risk of sampling vines from the same population.

The wild grapes were collected between August and September to ensure their complete morphological development, from vines which were growing far from vineyards to avoid any hybridisation. The pips were extracted, cleaned, dried and stored at 20 °C and 40% relative humidity.

Methods

Charring of reference grape pips

Grape pips from the 35 cultivated varieties, as well as from nine wild grapes were charred to be comparable with the charred archaeological material. This was done by using a bonfire, following the methodology of Uccesu et al. (2016). This method creates optimal comparison samples and also allows the charring of a large amount of reference material.

The bonfire was made in a pit in the ground, 30 cm deep and 1 m wide, and the grape pips were covered with 2 cm of topsoil to simulate the natural conditions of charring during 10 h of burning and cooling (ESM Fig. 1).

Digital image analysis

Digital images of archaeological and modern charred grape pips were acquired using an Epson V550 flatbed scanner with 400 dpi digital resolution. The scanning area did not exceed 1,024×1,024 pixels (Bacchetta et al. 2008). In order to represent the whole variability of the grape pips, the samples were scanned twice, the pips randomly placed on the scanner. For the modern grape pips, both wild and cultivars, a total of 7,000 and 1,198 images respectively were obtained. The archaeological samples were acquired only once, obtaining a total of 1,122 images, due to the large numbers involved.

The scanned images were binarized with ImageJ v. 1.49 (<http://rsb.info.nih.gov/ij>). A specific freely available plugin, Particles 8 (Landini 2006) (<https://blog.bham.ac.uk/intellimic/g-landini-software/>)

was used to record 26 morphometric features. In addition, 80 elliptic Fourier descriptors (EFDs) of the pip contour shapes were added using ImageJ v. 1.49 and a specific plugin developed by Diaz (2017). A total of 106 morphometric parameters were taken into consideration.

Statistical analysis

The measurements obtained from the digital grape pip image analyses contributed to a database of morphometric features. These data were statistically described by stepwise linear discriminant analysis (LDA), using the SPSS v. 16.0, to compare the modern with the archaeological pips, the latter being considered as an unidentified group. This approach is commonly used to classify and identify unknown groups that are characterised by quantitative variables, as in this case. LDA compares various known groups, looking for similarities and differences between them, and comparing the similarity of the unknown group with the known groups, according to morphometric parameters. LDA identifies and selects the best and the most statistically significant parameters among the 106 measured, using them to characterise seed samples (Bacchetta et al. 2010). Three statistical variables, the tolerance value, F-to-enter and F-to-remove values were used to define the power of each parameter and their role in the model. All variables with a value below 3.84 were excluded from the analysis (Venora et al. 2009). Lastly, a cross-validation procedure was applied to verify the performance of the identification system, with the leave one out cross validation (LOOCV) procedure (SPSS 2006).

Results

Discrimination of modern charred and uncharred grape pips

In order to test the validity of the discrimination of modern reference material, both charred and uncharred, a preliminary comparison between uncharred samples of cultivated and wild grape pips was done, achieving an overall correct identification of 100% (Table 1).

Similarly, we compared samples of charred cultivated and wild grape pips, obtaining an overall correct identification of 99.2% (Table 2).

Table 1 Linear discriminant analysis results showing percentages of correct identification of uncharred samples of *Vitis vinifera* ssp. *vinifera* and *V. vinifera* ssp. *sylvestris* pips

	ssp. <i>vinifera</i>	ssp. <i>sylvestris</i>	Total
ssp. <i>vinifera</i>	100 (6,909)	0.01 (1)	100 (6,910)
ssp. <i>sylvestris</i>	–	100 (952)	100 (952)
Overall			100% (7,862)

The numbers of analysed seeds are in brackets

Table 2 Percentages of correct identification of samples of charred *Vitis vinifera* ssp. *vinifera* and *V. vinifera* ssp. *sylvestris* pips, from linear discriminant analysis

	ssp. <i>vinifera</i>	ssp. <i>sylvestris</i>	Total
ssp. <i>vinifera</i>	99.8 (6,820)	0.2 (14)	100 (6,834)
ssp. <i>sylvestris</i>	5.3 (46)	94.7 (820)	100 (866)
Overall			99.2% (7,700)

The numbers of analysed seeds are in brackets

Morphometric comparison between archaeological and modern charred grape pips

With the aim of identifying the archaeological grape pips to species, the sample of archaeological pips was compared with the charred modern accessions of 35 cultivars and four populations of wild grape. Before the statistical analysis, the raw data were standardised, detecting a total of 330 outliers in the charred modern material, both cultivars and wild, which were not considered in the discriminant analysis, resulting in a total of 6,834 images of the cultivars and 866 of the wild grapes.

From the LDA comparison between the archaeological grape pips, which were considered individually and added to the classifier as unknown groups, and the charred modern *V. vinifera* ssp. *vinifera* and ssp. *sylvestris* pips, the overall level of correct identification was 99.2 % (Table 3). The archaeological grape pips from Torre dos Namorados were identified as ssp. *sylvestris* in 60.5% and ssp. *vinifera* in 39.5% of the cases (Table 3).

Table 3 Percentages of correct identification of samples of charred *Vitis vinifera* ssp. *vinifera*, *V. vinifera* ssp. *sylvestris* and archaeological grape pips from Torre dos Namorados (considered as an unknown group), from linear discriminant analysis

Charred	ssp. <i>vinifera</i>	ssp. <i>sylvestris</i>	Total
ssp. <i>vinifera</i>	99.8 (6,820)	0.2 (14)	100 (6834)
ssp. <i>sylvestris</i>	5.3 (46)	94.7 (820)	100 (866)
Torre dos Namorados	39.5 (443)	60.5 (679)	100 (1122)
Overall			99.2% (8,822)

The numbers of analysed seeds are in brackets

Morphometric comparison between modern charred wild and archaeological grape pips

Before analysing the archaeological grape pips which showed morphological similarities to wild ones, we performed a preliminary comparative analysis between the samples of uncharred pips from the four wild grape populations and the LDA results showed that 67.7 to 79.0% of them were distinguishable from each other (Table 4).

Similar results were obtained from the comparison between charred pips from the four wild grape populations. The LDA results showed that 61.4 to 79.9% of the pip samples were, again, distinguishable from each other (Table 5).

The archaeological pips that showed similarities to wild ones (60.5%) were finally compared with the samples of charred pips from the four wild populations. The archaeological samples were added individually to the classifier as an unknown group. The archaeological pips showed a high degree of similarity with the wild grapes from Portel and Castelo Branco in 43.5 and 34.8% of the cases, respectively (Table 5).

Table 4 Percentages of correct identification of samples of uncharred pips from four wild populations of *Vitis vinifera* ssp. *sylvestris*, from linear discriminant analysis. The numbers of analysed seeds are in brackets

	Alcaçer do Sal	Castelo Branco	Montemor o Novo	Portel	Total
Alcaçer do Sal	72.0 (139)	2.6 (5)	4.7 (9)	20.7 (40)	100 (193)
Castelo Branco	3.4 (10)	67.7 (199)	20.4 (60)	8.5 (25)	100 (294)
Montemor o Novo	2.7 (1)	21.6 (8)	64.9 (24)	10.8 (4)	100 (37)
Portel	12.6 (54)	4.7 (20)	3.7 (16)	79.0 (338)	100 (428)
Overall					73.5% (866)

Table 5 Percentages of correct identification of charred pips from four populations of *Vitis vinifera* ssp. *sylvestris* and the archaeological pips Torre dos Namorados (considered as an unknown group), from linear discriminant analysis. The numbers of analysed seeds are in brackets, in bold, the highest values of correct identification.

	Alcaçer do Sal	Castelo Branco	Montemor o Novo	Portel	Total
Alcaçer do Sal	70.6 (96)	5.1 (17)	5.9 (8)	18.4 (25)	100 (136)
Castelo Branco	5.9 (16)	77.1 (209)	10.3 (28)	6.6 (18)	100 (271)
Montemor o Novo	7.0 (4)	17.5 (10)	61.4 (35)	14.0 (8)	100 (57)
Portel	10.9 (44)	5.0 (20)	4.2 (17)	79.9 (321)	100 (402)
Torre dos Namorados	19.8 (138)	34.8 (242)	1.9 (13)	43.5 (303)	100 (696)
Overall					76.3% (866)

Morphometric comparison between modern grape cultivars and archaeological grape pips

The 39.5% of archaeological pips that showed similarities to cultivated grapes were considered individually as unknown groups when they were compared with the pips from the 35 native grape cultivars. The archaeological pips showed close morphological similarities with 18 modern cultivars, in particular, the highest percentages were those with similarities to three white grape varieties, Tamarez (44.8%), Samarrinho (12%), Rabigato (10.6%) and two black grape cultivars, Trincadeira Preta (8.0%) and Aragonez (15.7%) (Table 6, Fig. 6).

Table 6 Percentages of correct identification of charred pips of *Vitis vinifera* ssp. *vinifera* cultivars and archaeological pips from Torre dos Namorados, from linear discriminant analysis. The numbers of analysed seeds are in brackets, in bold, the highest values of correct identification

Code	Cultivar name	Charred cultivar classification (%)	Torre dos Namorados seeds classification (%)
41209	Alvarelhão Ceitão	37.6 (73)	-
41302	Barreto	21.2 (39)	0.7 (3)
41303	Castelõa	39.0 (71)	1.2 (5)
50607	Tinta Gorda	39.2 (67)	0.2 (1)
50705	Touriga Brasileira	48.5 (95)	-
50711	Alicante Branco	59.3 (112)	0.5 (2)
51002	Castelã	34.4 (55)	0.5 (2)
51117	Bastardo Branca	25.6 (50)	0.2 (1)
51316	Sarigo	36.2 (51)	-
51411	Dorinto	29.9 (46)	-
51516	Samarrinho	47.5 (85)	12.0 (51)
51514	Folha de Figueira	18.9 (34)	-
52004	Cornifesto	27.0 (51)	-
52014	Rabigato	44.1 (89)	10.6 (45)
52102	Tinta Carvalha	30.5 (74)	-
52112	Gouveio	24.9 (48)	-
52206	Touriga Nacional	39.9 (77)	-
52307	Donzelinho Branco	64.0 (128)	-
52309	Boal Ratinho	17.7 (49)	-
52310	Avesso	60.9 (112)	0.2 (1)
52410	Cerceal Branco	17.8 (38)	0.5 (2)
52507	Batoca	39.6 (78)	0.2 (1)
52513	Diagalves	43.1 (84)	-
52709	Folgasão	18.8 (36)	-
53205	Malvasia Preta	49.6 (65)	-
53307	Tinto Cão	37.2 (113)	0.9 (4)
52314	Fonte Cal	17.0 (38)	-
53006	Trincadeira Preta	29.6 (56)	8.0 (34)
52403	Camarate	13.8 (38)	-
51410	Douradinha	43.2 (79)	2.6 (11)
51412	Arinto do Interior	42.1 (69)	0.9 (4)
51211	Uva Cavaco	65.6 (126)	0.2 (1)

52002	Marufo	18.7 (43)	-
51910	Tamarez	44.3 (112)	44.8 (191)
52603	Aragonez	40.0 (34)	15.7 (67)
Overall		35.3% (6,835)	35.3% (426)

Fig. 6 Linear discriminant analysis (LDA) diagram comparing the charred grape pips from Torre de Namorados with those of modern cultivated varieties; the numbers are the percentages of the total number of archaeological pips identified as particular cultivars

Discussion

In recent time, morphometric analyses of archaeobotanical remains have been considered useful for the discrimination between pips from wild and domesticated grapes (Cunha et al. 2007b; Terral et al. 2010; Bouby et al. 2013; Pagnoux et al. 2015; Sabato et al. 2015; Ucchesu et al. 2017). However, the deformation of pips in shape and size caused by charring results in an overlap in dimensions between wild and domesticated shapes, making this methodology ineffective for identifying charred archaeological remains. Some researchers have argued that the main problem arises from the use of small reference collections (Bouby et al. 2018). In recent years, morphometric studies based on large reference collections have shown that it is possible to identify charred archaeological grape pips when assemblages are large and well preserved (Ucchesu et al. 2016; Bouby et al. 2018). Additionally, the use of image analysis technology and statistical analysis on archaeobotanical materials such as seeds and fruits has been proven to be a reproducible method to characterise and distinguish wild forms

from domesticated ones (Terral et al. 2010; Bouby et al. 2013; Pagnoux et al. 2015; Sabato et al. 2015; Ucchesu et al. 2017).

In this work, image analysis techniques and LDA analysis of modern pips from cultivated and wild grapes from Portugal has shown that it is possible to reliably identify both uncharred and charred pips using modern charred grape pips as comparative material and has allowed us to identify the types of grapes used at the Roman winery of Torre dos Namorados.

The archaeological grape pips showed the most similarity to the wild ones, while a few matched domesticated grape pips.

The clear association between the archaeological and wild pips, in particular with the populations from Portel (Alentejo region, roughly 200 km from the site, 43.5%) and from Castelo Branco (Beiras region, in the vicinity of the site, 34.8%) suggest that wild grapes may have been used for wine making at around 400 CE in Torres dos Namorados.

We do not know if this use of wild grapes was a common practice in this region, or if Torre dos Namorados was an isolated case. However, the use of both wild and cultivated grapes for wine making has already been found from previous morphometric studies of Roman grape pip assemblages from several Mediterranean areas (Queiroz and Mateus 2007; Figueiral et al. 2010; Bouby et al. 2013; Boso et al. 2020).

Some authors have speculated that the use of wild grapes for making wine in Roman times was probably related to the slow process of grape domestication, which was then still underway in the western Mediterranean (Bouby et al. 2013), but a possible “wine economic crisis” is not ruled out. We do not exclude that a similar event may have also occurred at Roman Torre dos Namorados, where a shortage of cultivated grapes might have necessitated the use of wild grapes for wine.

However, the discriminant analysis also showed the presence of a small amount of domesticated grapes in the assemblage. The comparison between the grape pips from Torre dos Namorados and those from the 35 Portuguese native grape cultivars showed morphological similarities with 18 of them, in particular with the Tamarez, Aragonez, Samarrinho, Rabigato and Trincadeira Preta cultivars (Table 6).

Moreover, our results showed that most of the cultivars similar to archaeological pips, in particular Tamarez, Samarrinho and Rabigato, in descending order respectively, have white grapes (Table 6).

Tamarez was grown more frequently in the past, but nowadays it is considered a minor cultivar, at risk of extinction. It was grown mainly in the north and centre of Portugal, and it had other names according to the region, such as Trincadeira (in the Douro region); Arinto Gordo (Dão); Boal de Figueira (Bairrada); Boal de Santarém (Beira Litoral); Boal Prior and Dona Branca (Bairrada) and

local names such as Molinho do Vau (Alcobaça, Bombarral, Óbidos); Roupeiro (Caldas Rainha); Santo Estevão (Atalaia, Merceana) (Alarte 1712; Eiras-Dias et al. 2011).

The white grape cultivars Rabigato and Samarrinho are known from the literature (Lobo de Lacerda 1790; Sousa Figueredo 1875). Regarding the origin of these cultivars, it is known that Cayetana Blanca (Sarigo in Portugal) and Savagnin or Traminer are their respective progenitors (VIVC 2022). Both were considered minor varieties until ten years ago, as they were cultivated in very limited areas or even not at all, so risking their extinction. This is one of the reasons for the importance of their preservation in the national germplasm banks. Information about these grapes is currently well documented in the catalogue of grape varieties suitable for making wine in Portugal (Eiras-Dias et al. 2011, 2013).

Many white grape varieties are still grown nowadays and used for winemaking in this area of Portugal (IVV 2021). These results confirm the theory that white grapes were used to make wine at Roman Torre dos Namorados. Several morphometric studies of ancient grape pips have already revealed the use of a mixture of different types of grapes for wine making, both wild and cultivated, including the use of cultivated white grapes in the Roman period (Queiroz and Mateus 2007; Figueiral et al. 2010; Bouby et al. 2013; Boso et al. 2020).

Taking into consideration all this information, we can assume that a selection of different types of both wild and cultivated grapes were used for wine making at Roman Torre dos Namorados. The history of viticulture in the Roman province of Lusitania is complex, and chemical or genomic analyses on archaeobotanical material would provide more information in this field. Nevertheless, many difficulties still exist nowadays in the extraction of genetic material from charred archaeological seeds (Bacilieri et al. 2017). For these reasons, the results from this work represent an important first step in elucidating the history of Roman viticulture in this region.

Conclusions

Even if we are still far from a full understanding of the history of viticulture in Roman Lusitania, our morphometric study of the charred grape pips from Torre dos Namorados provides the first such information from this region. Above all, we must consider the rarity of these archaeological finds in Portugal and the difficulties that currently exist in the extraction of genetic material from charred archaeological seeds.

The clear association between some of the archaeological grape pips and modern examples from wild grapes growing in Portugal leads us to speculate that wild grapes were used for making wine in Roman Torre dos Namorados.

Results from this study also showed a clear association between some of the archaeological grape pips and modern ones from Portuguese white grape varieties. Further investigations in this field using a wider database that includes grape pips from different Mediterranean areas are expected to provide a more comprehensive view of Roman viticulture in Portugal.

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References

- Alarcão J (2005) Ainda sobre a localização dos povos referidos na inscrição da ponte de Alcântara. In: Lusitanos e Romanos no Nordeste da Lusitânia. Actas das 2.as Jornadas do Património da Beira Interior. Centro de Estudos Ibéricos, Guarda, pp 119-132
- Alarte V (1712) Agricultura das vinhas, e tudo o que pertence a ellas até perfeito recolhimento do vinho, e relação das suas virtudes, e da cepa, vides, folhas, e borras. Officina Real Deslandesiana, Lisboa
- Almadanim MC, Baleiras-Couto MM, Pereira HS et al (2007) Genetic diversity of the grapevine (*Vitis vinifera* L.) varieties most utilized for wine production in Portugal. *Vitis* 46:111–116
- Almeida CAB (1996) O Cultivo da vinha na antiguidade clássica na Região Demarcada no Douro: ponto da situação. *DOURO: Estudos & Documentos* 1:18-30
- Almeida FD, Veiga Ferreira O (1967) Um poço Lusitano-Romano encontrado em Idanha-a-Velha. *O Arqueólogo Português* 1(3ª série):57-63

- Ângelo MJ (2012) Torre dos Namorados (Quintas da Torre, Fundão) – Do aglomerado urbano secundário romano à Comenda Medieval. Dissertação de Mestrado em Arqueologia e Território, orientada pela Doutora Maria da Conceição Lopes, apresentada ao Departamento de História, Arqueologia e Artes da Faculdade de Letras da Universidade de Coimbra, Coimbra
- Ângelo MJ, Ribeiro CA (2008) Torre dos Namorados (Quintas da Torre, Vale Prazeres, Fundão). 1os Resultados da Campanha de escavação arqueológica Coitos 2006. *Eburobriga* 5:27-52
- Arnold C, Gillet F, Gobat JM (1998) Situation de la vigne sauvage *Vitis vinifera* ssp. *silvestris* en Europe. *Vitis* 37:159-170
- Arruda AM (2008) Fenícios e púnicos em Portugal: problemas e perspectivas. In: Vita JP, Zamora JÁ (eds) *Nuevas Perspectivas II: la arqueología fenicia y púnica en la Península Ibérica*. Universidad Pompeu Fabra, Barcelona, pp 13-23
- Bacchetta G, Grillo O, Mattana E, Venora G (2008) Morpho-colorimetric characterization by image analysis to identify diaspores of wild plant species. *Flora - Morphol Distrib Funct Ecol Plants* 203:669-682. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.flora.2007.11.004>
- Bacchetta G, Grillo O, Lovicu G et al (2010) Pips Image Analysis to support Cultivar Identification of *Vitis vinifera* L. *CIGR Workshop on Image Analysis in Agriculture* 2010:30-35
- Bacilieri R, Bouby L, Figueiral I et al (2017) Potential of combining morphometry and ancient DNA information to investigate grapevine domestication. *Veget Hist Archaeobot* 26:345-356. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00334-016-0597-4>
- Barnard H, Dooley AN, Areshian G, Gasparyan B, Faull KF (2011) Chemical evidence for wine production around 4000 BCE in the Late Chalcolithic Near Eastern highlands. *J Archaeol Sci* 38:977-984. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jas.2010.11.012>
- Barros L (1998) Introdução à pré e proto-história de Almada. Câmara Municipal de Almada, Almada
- Barros L (2001) Quinta do Almaraz: o principio de Almada cidade. *Anais de Almada* 4:11-24
- Boso S, Gago P, Santiago JL et al (2020) Morphometric comparison of current, Roman-era and medieval *Vitis* seeds from the north-west of Spain. *Aus J Grape Wine Res* 26:300-309
- Bouby L, Bonhomme V, Ivorra S et al (2018) Back from burn out: are experimentally charred grapevine pips too distorted to be characterized using morphometrics? *Archaeol Anthropol Sci* 10:943-954. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12520-016-0425-x>
- Bouby L, Figueiral I, Bouchette A et al (2013) Bioarchaeological Insights into the Process of Domestication of Grapevine (*Vitis vinifera* L.) during Roman Times in Southern France. *PLoS One* 8:e0063195. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0063195>
- Brun J-P (2011) Viticulture et oléiculture en Gaule. In: Ouzoulias P, Tranoy L (eds) *Comment les Gaules devinrent romaines*. La Découverte, Paris, pp 231-253
- Carvalho PC (2007) Cova da Beira – Ocupação e exploração do território na época romana. *Conimbriga / Anexos* 4. Câmara Municipal do Fundão, Instituto de Arqueologia da Faculdade de Letras da Universidade de Coimbra (IAFLUC), Coimbra

- Cunha J, Baleiras-Couto M, Cunha JP et al (2007a) Characterization of Portuguese populations of *Vitis vinifera* L. ssp. *sylvestris* (Gmelin) Hegi. *Genet Resour Crop Evol* 54:981-988. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10722-006-9189-y>
- Cunha J, Cunha LP, Carneiro LC, Fevereiro MP, Eiras-Dias J-E (2007b) Carpometria da grainha na identificação de ancestrais selvagens de “*Vitis vinifera*” L. *Ciência Téc Vitiv* 22:29-34
- Cunha J, Ibáñez J, Teixeira-Santos M et al (2016) Characterisation of the Portuguese grapevine germplasm with 48 single-nucleotide polymorphisms. *Aust J Grape Wine Res* 22:504-516. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ajgw.12225>
- Curado FP (2006) Reflexões em torno do terminus augustalis (dito) de Peroviseu. *Eburobriga* 4:99-119
- Currás A, Costa AM, Freitas MdC, Danielsen R, Bugalhão J (2021) Landscape change and vegetation history in the city of Lisbon during Roman times and the Early Medieval Period. *Holocene* 31:134-144
- Diaz G (2017) Contour recognition of complex leaf shapes. *PLoS One* 12:e0189427. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0189427>
- Eiras-Dias JE, Faustino R, Clímaco P et al (2011) Catálogo das castas para vinho cultivadas em Portugal, vol. 1. Instituto da Vinha e do Vinho I.P., Lisboa
- Eiras-Dias JE, Faustino R, Clímaco P et al (2013) Catálogo das castas para vinho cultivadas em Portugal, vol. 2. Instituto da Vinha e do Vinho I.P., Lisboa
- Evans SJ (2018) The wines of northern Spain: From Galicia to the Pyrenees and Rioja to the Basque Country. Infinite Ideas, Oxford
- Fabião C (1998) O vinho na Lusitânia: reflexões em torno de um problema arqueológico. *Rev Portuguesa Arqueologia* 1:169-198
- FAOSTAT (2022) Food and agriculture organisation data, <http://faostat.fao.org/>. Date accessed 15/02/2022
- Figueiral I, Bouby L, Buffat L, Petitot H, Terral J-F (2010) Archaeobotany, vine growing and wine producing in Roman Southern France: the site of Gasquinoy (Béziers, Hérault). *J Archaeol Sci* 37:139-149. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jas.2009.09.024>
- Fletcher WJ, Boski T, Moura D (2007) Palynological evidence for environmental and climatic change in the lower Guadiana valley, Portugal, during the last 13 000 years. *Holocene* 17:481-494. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0959683607077027>
- Freitas S, Gazda MA, Rebelo MÂ et al (2021) Pervasive hybridization with local wild relatives in Western European grapevine varieties. *Sci Adv* 7:eabi8584. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.abi8584>
- Guerra A (2007) Sobre o território e a sede dos Lancienses (Oppidani e Transcudani) e outras questões conexas. *Conimbriga* 46:161-206
- Imazio S, Labra M, Grassi F, Scienza A, Failla O (2006) Chloroplast microsatellites to investigate the origin of grapevine. *Genet Resour Crop Evol* 53:1,003-1,011. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10722-004-6896-0>
- IVV (2021) Instituto da vinha e do vinho (Institute of wine and vine), Ministério da Agricultura (Ministry of Agriculture). <https://www.ivv.gov.pt/np4/112/np4/318.html>, consulted on 24/09/2021)

- Kroll H (1991) Südosteuropa. In: van Zeist W, Wasylikowa K, Behre K-E (eds) Progress in Old World Palaeoethnobotany: A retrospective view on the occasion of 20 years of the International Work Group for Palaeoethnobotany. Balkema, Rotterdam, pp 161-177
- Landini G (2006) Quantitative analysis of the epithelial lining architecture in radicular cysts and odontogenic keratocysts. *Head Face Med* 2:1-9. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1746-160X-2-4>
- Levadoux L (1956) Les populations sauvages et cultivées de *Vitis vinifera* L. *Ann de l'Amélioration des Plantes* 6:59-117
- Lobo de Lacerda CB (1790) Memória sobre a cultura das vinhas de Portugal. In: Cardoso JL (ed) (Memórias Económicas da Academia Real das Ciências de Lisboa, Tomo 2) Na Officina da Mesma Academia, Lisboa, pp 16-134 e 198-284
- Magris G, Jurman I, Fornasiero et al (2021) The genomes of 204 *Vitis vinifera* accessions reveal the origin of European wine grapes. *Nat Commun* 12:7240
- Marvelli S, De'Siena S, Rizzoli E, Marchesini M (2013) The origin of grapevine cultivation in Italy: The archaeobotanical evidence. *Annali Bot* 3:155-163. <https://doi.org/10.4462/annbotrm-10326>
- McGovern PE (2003) Ancient Wine: The search for the origins of viniculture. Princeton University Press, Princeton
- McGovern PE, Hartung U, Badler VR, Glusker DL, Exner LJ (1997) The beginnings of winemaking and viniculture in the ancient Near East and Egypt
- Moricca C, Bouby L, Bonhomme V et al (2021) Grapes and vines of the Phoenicians: Morphometric analyses of pips from modern varieties and Iron Age archaeological sites in the Western Mediterranean. *J Archaeol Sci: Rep* 37:102991
- Negrul AM (1946) Origin and classification of cultivated grape. In: Baranov A, Kai YF, Lazarevski MA, Negrul AM, Palibin TV, Prosmoserdov NN (eds) Ampelografiia SSSR (Ampelography of the USSR). Gostekh i Ekonom Izdat Pischepromizdat, Moskow, pp 159-216
- Olmo HP (1996) The Origin and Domestication of the *Vinifera* grape. In: McGovern PE, Fleming SJ, Katz SH (eds) The Origins and Ancient History of Wine. Routledge, London, pp 31-43
- Pagnoux C, Bouby L, Ivorra S et al (2015) Inferring the agrobiodiversity of *Vitis vinifera* L. (grapevine) in ancient Greece by comparative shape analysis of archaeological and modern seeds. *Veget Hist Archaeobot* 24:75-84. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00334-014-0482-y>
- Peña-Chocarro L, Pérez-Jordà G, Alonso N et al (2019) Roman and medieval crops in the Iberian Peninsula: A first overview of seeds and fruits from archaeological sites. *Quat Int* 499:49-66. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quaint.2017.09.037>
- Pereira PA (2017) O Vinho na Lusitânia. Centro de Investigação Transdisciplinar «Cultura, Espaço e Memória» (CITCEM), Porto
- Pereira PA, Silvino T (2018) Trás do Castelo (Vale de Mir, Pegarinhos, Alijó) - a roman agricultural settlement on the verge of the first century AD. In: Fontes L, Cruz G, Alves M (eds) Cultural Interactions and Changing Landscapes in Europe (2nd century BC / 2nd century AD): The international Symposium, Boticas, 11/12/13 October 2018. Unidade de Arqueologia da Universidade do Minho, Braga, pp 160-163
- Pérez Losada, Fermín (2002) estudio arqueohistórico dos "aglomerados secundarios" romanos en Galicia. (Brigantium 13) Boletín do Museo Arqueolóxico e Histórico da Coruña

- Pinto da Silva AR (1988) A Paleoetnobotânica na Arqueologia Portuguesa. Resultados desde 1931 a 1987. In: Queiroga F, Sousa IM, Oliveira CM (eds) Actas do encontro "Paleoecologia e Arqueologia. Câmara Municipal de Vila Nova de Famalicão, Vila Nova de Famalicão, pp 5-36
- Queiroga F (1992) War and Castros: New approaches to the northwestern Portuguese Iron Age. (BAR International Series 1198) British Archaeological Reports, Oxford
- Queiroz PF, Mateus JE (2007) Acerca das Graínhas de Uva da Idade do Ferro de Castro Marim. (Trabalhos do Cipa 105) CIPA – IPA, Lisboa
- Queiroz PF, Mateus JE, van Leeuwen W, Pereira T, Pereira D (2006) Castro marim e o seu território imediato durante a antiguidade. Paleo-etno-botânica. Relatório final. (Trabalhos do Cipa 95) CIPA – IPA, Lisboa. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.25361.63848>
- Rego PR, Aira Rodriguez MJ (1993) A palaeocarpological study of Neolithic and Bronze Age levels of the Buraco da Pala rock-shelter (Bragança, Portugal). *Veget Hist Archaeobot* 2:163-172. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00198587>
- Sabato D, Esteras C, Grillo O, Picó B, Bacchetta G (2015) Seeds morpho-colourimetric analysis as complementary method to molecular characterization of melon diversity. *Sci Horticulture-Amsterdam* 192:441-452. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scienta.2015.06.006>
- Savo V, Kumbaric A, Caneva G (2016) Grapevine (*Vitis Vinifera* L.) symbolism in the ancient Euro-Mediterranean cultures. *Econ Bot* 70:190-197. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12231-016-9347-x>
- Scossiroli RE (1988) Origine ed evoluzione della vite. *Atti Ist Bot e Lab Critt* 7:35-55
- Seabra LCN (2015) Estudo Paleoetnobotânico do Povoado da Idade do Ferro do Crastoeiro (Noroeste de Portugal). Dissertação de Mestrado. Universidade do Minho, Braga
- Sefc KM, Steinkellner H, Lefort F et al (2003) Evaluation of the genetic contribution of local wild vines to European grapevine cultivars. *Am J Enol Vitic* 54:15-21
- Sousa Figueredo A (1875) Manual de Arboricultura. Tratado Theorico e Prático da Cultura e Exploração das Árvores Fructíferas, a cultura da vinha. Livraria Internacional de Ernesto Chardron (Porto) e Eugenio Chardron (Braga)
- SPSS (2006) Application guide (Prentice Hall: Upper Saddle River, NJ, USA). Base 15.0
- Tereso JPV (2012) Environmental Change, agricultural development and social trends in NW Iberia from the Late Prehistory to the Late Antiquity. Doctoral Thesis, Biology Department, Faculty of Sciences, University of Porto, Porto
- Tereso JP, Cruz G (2014) Frutos e Sementes da Idade do Ferro e Época Romana da Citânia de Briteiros. *Al Madan* 19:83-91
- Tereso JP, Ramil-Rego P, Almeida-da-Silva R (2011) A exploração de recursos alimentares silvestres e seu enquadramento nas dinâmicas económicas e sociais das comunidades agrícolas desde a pré-história à época romana. In: Tereso JP, Honrado JP, Pinto AT, Rego FC (eds) Florestas no Norte de Portugal: História, Ecologia e Desafios de Gestão. InBio - Rede de Investigação em Biodiversidade e Biologia Evolutiva, Porto, pp 56-83
- Tereso JP, Ramil-Rego P, Almeida-da-Silva R (2013a) Roman agriculture in the conventus Bracaraugustanus (NW Iberia). *J Archaeol Sci* 40:2,848-2,858. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jas.2013.01.006>

Tereso JP, Ramil-Rego P, De Carvalho TP, Almeida-da-Silva R, Var FC (2013b) Crops and fodder: Evidence for storage and processing activities in a functional area at the Roman settlement of Monte Mozinho (northern Portugal). *Veget Hist Archaeobot* 22:479-492. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00334-013-0399-x>

Terral J-F, Tabard E, Bouby L et al (2010) Evolution and history of grapevine (*Vitis vinifera*) under domestication: new morphometric perspectives to understand seed domestication syndrome and reveal origins of ancient European cultivars. *Ann Bot* 105:443-455. <https://doi.org/10.1093/aob/mcp298>

This P, Lacombe T, Thomas MR (2006) Historical origins and genetic diversity of wine grapes. *Trends Genet* 22:511-519. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tig.2006.07.008>

Ucchesu M, Orrù M, Grillo O et al (2015) Earliest evidence of a primitive cultivar of *Vitis vinifera* L. during the Bronze Age in Sardinia (Italy). *Veget Hist Archaeobot* 24:587-600. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00334-014-0512-9>

Ucchesu M, Orrù M, Grillo O et al (2016) Predictive method for correct identification of archaeological charred grape seeds: Support for advances in knowledge of grape domestication process. *PLoS One* 11:e0149814. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0149814>

Ucchesu M, Sarigu M, Del Vais C et al (2017) First finds of *Prunus domestica* L. in Italy from the Phoenician and Punic periods (6th-2nd centuries BC). *Veget Hist Archaeobot* 26:539-549. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00334-017-0622-2>

Vaz JI (1977) Inscrições Romanas do Museu do Fundão, Conimbriga 16:5-32

Valamoti SM, Mangafa M, Koukouli-Chrysanthaki C, Malamidou D (2007) Grape-pressings from northern Greece: the earliest wine in the Aegean? *Antiquity* 81:54-61. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0003598X00094837>

Venora G, Grillo O, Ravalli C, Cremonini R (2009) Identification of Italian landraces of bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.) using an image analysis system. *Sci Hortic-Amsterdam* 121:410-418

VIVC (2022) *Vitis International Variety Catalogue*, Julius-Kühn Institut, <https://www.vivc.de/index.php?r=cultivarname%2Findex>, consulted on 24/09/2021

Wen J, Lu L-M, Nie Z-L et al (2018) A new phylogenetic tribal classification of the grape family (Vitaceae). *J Syst Evol* 56:262-272. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jse.12427>

Zohary D (1995) The domestication of the grapevine *Vitis vinifera* L. in the Near East. In: McGovern PE, Fleming SJ, Katz SH (eds) *The Origins and Ancient History of Wine*. Routledge, London, pp 23-30

Zohary D, Hopf M, Weiss E (2012) *Domestication of Plants in the Old World: The origin and spread of domesticated plants in Southwest Asia, Europe, and the Mediterranean Basin*. Oxford University Press, Oxford

Statements and Declarations

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.